

POST RENAL TRANSPLANT CARDIOVASCULAR REMODELING: A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL SINGLE CENTER STUDY BASED ON ECHOCARDIOGRAPHIC FINDINGS

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Abstract

Objectives:

Cardiovascular comorbidities secondarily to End Stage Renal Disease is one of the major determinants of early morbidity and mortality. Structural abnormalities such as Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH), systolic dysfunction, and impaired arterial compliance are common among such patients. Renal transplantation is the game changer, that not only improves renal functions but also reverses cardiac defects. This study aimed to compare cardiac structural and functional abnormalities pre- and post-renal transplantation.

Methods:

We conducted a quasi-experimental study including 65 ESRD patients who underwent kidney transplantation and were followed for 12 months. Echocardiographic parameters, including left ventricular mass index (LVMI) and ejection fraction (EF), along with blood pressure and electrolyte status, were assessed pre- and post-transplant. The primary endpoints were regression of LVMI and improvement in systolic function (EF). Secondary outcomes included blood pressure control and normalization of electrolyte balance. Paired t-tests, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, and chi-square tests were applied as appropriate.

Results:

At 12 months post-transplant, significant improvements were observed across cardiac parameters. Mean EF improved from $37.4 \pm 5.8\%$ to $44.8 \pm 7.2\%$ ($p < 0.001$), with 66.1% of patients showing a clinically meaningful recovery. LVMI decreased significantly from $141.6 \pm 18.5 \text{ g/m}^2$ to $116.5 \pm 15.3 \text{ g/m}^2$ ($p < 0.001$). Blood pressure improved markedly, with mean systolic BP reducing from $159.7 \pm 11.2 \text{ mmHg}$ to $136.0 \pm 10.7 \text{ mmHg}$ ($p < 0.001$), and 68% achieving optimal control ($<130/80 \text{ mmHg}$) at follow-up. Electrolyte balance, including potassium and calcium-phosphate, normalized in the majority of patients.

Conclusion:

Kidney transplantation leads to a significant reversal of adverse cardiac

remodeling, including regression of LVH and improvement in systolic function, alongside better blood pressure control and electrolyte normalization. These findings highlight the potential of renal transplantation not only as a renal replacement therapy but also as a key intervention in cardiovascular recovery in ESRD patients. Further multicenter studies with longer follow-up are warranted to refine post-transplant cardiovascular management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Kidney transplantation is the gold standard treatment for individuals suffering from End Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) [1]. Pakistan ranks fifth most prevalent country with ESRD according to National Kidney Foundation summit 2024. It is reported that each year over 100 new cases are documented per million population in Pakistan [2]. This is due to higher prevalence of Diabetes and Hypertension in the region which remain undiagnosed due to lack of awareness, inaccessible facilities and misguidance. Patients usually present with complications leading to higher morbidity and mortality.

Unfortunately, ESRD whatever the underlying cause is, associated with increased cardiovascular events and complications due to hemodynamic instability, lack of vascular access, arrhythmias and left ventricular dysfunctions [3]. This picture may event get worsen when the patients does not receive appropriate renal replacement therapies.

It has been observed that left ventricular enlargement along with weakened pumping ability during both contraction and relaxation phases are commonly identified as significant indicators of poorer cardiovascular outcomes among patients on dialysis [4]. In advanced chronic kidney disease (CKD), the heart muscle faces a range of complex metabolic stresses triggered by uremia-related inflammation, oxidative stress, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, deficiency in calcitriol, heightened levels of fibroblast growth factor (FGF), and alterations in mineral metabolism. These stressors lead to an enlargement of heart muscles, decreased blood vessel supply within the heart, the formation of non-blood vessel related fibrous tissue, as well as hardening of arteries and reduced flexibility in their walls. Combined, these structural changes

diminish the cardiac efficiency in pumping blood and escalate the energy required by the heart and its consumption of oxygen (3, 4, 5).

Renal transplantation in candidates with active cardiac disease is a complex clinical phenomenon. In ESRD patients, progressive Cardio Renal Syndrome (CRS) often culminates in poor cardiovascular outcomes and is one of the predominant reasons for mortality in such individuals (6). However, a growing body of knowledge suggests that renal transplant can be pursued even in candidates with active cardiac disease. Studies have done which showed that renal transplantation has restored cardiac function to a considerable extent (7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13). In the present study, we intend to assess the cardiovascular functional capacity in individuals with ESRD both pre and post renal transplant via transthoracic echocardiography and to examine any functional and structural changes in their cardiovascular system during this process.

1. Materials and Methods:

1.1. Study Design, Settings and Location:

This was a quasi-experimental, non-randomized study. This study was conducted at the Renal Transplant Unit of Dow University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan, between January 2024 and December 2024. The unit provides comprehensive renal transplantation services with structured postoperative follow-up and cardiovascular monitoring. Echocardiographic and cardiovascular assessments were carried out in collaboration with the Department of Cardiology of the same institution.

1.2. Sample size estimation and recruitment of participant:

The sample size was calculated as 54 by using PASS version 24 (NCSS, Kaysville, Utah, USA) software, based on two sample t-test assuming equal variance by entering difference with 95% confidence of interval, 80% power of test, 5% margin of error, keeping alpha 0.20, the prevalence of cardiovascular complications on patients receiving RRTs was 7 (9.4 %) [4], in an estimated population of 151 within a year.

A total of 65 consecutive patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) undergoing kidney transplantation during the study period were recruited. Subjects aged between 18–65 years with ESRD with planned renal transplantation were included in the study. Patients with preexisting cardiac disease unrelated to ESRD, severe systemic infection, or inability to provide informed consent were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to study enrollment.

Echocardiographic and Hemodynamic Assessments:

Pre-transplant cardiac evaluations were performed one month prior to surgery, and follow-up assessments were conducted at 12 months post-transplant. Cardiac structure and function were assessed using echocardiography and cardiovascular biomarkers.

Each echocardiographic evaluation included measurement of interventricular septal (IVS) thickness, posterior wall (PW) thickness, and left ventricular diastolic and systolic dimensions (LVDd and LVDs). Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was calculated using the biplane Simpson's method. Left ventricular (LV) mass was estimated using the American Society of Echocardiography (ASE) formula:

$$LV\ mass = 0.8 \times [1.04 \times \{(IVS + PW + LVDd)^3 - LVDd^3\}] + 0.6$$

LV mass was indexed to body surface area (LVMI). Systolic function was categorized as normal or abnormal based on mitral inflow patterns and tissue Doppler imaging. Right ventricular systolic pressure (RVSP) was estimated from tricuspid regurgitation velocity using the modified Bernoulli equation.

Assessment of Structural and Vascular Changes

- Left Ventricular Remodeling: Evaluated using LVMI, LV dimensions (LVDd and LVDs), and LVEF.
- Vascular Stiffness: Measured using pulse wave velocity (PWV), with higher values indicating greater arterial stiffness.
- Chamber Dimensions: IVS and PW thickness were assessed in diastole to identify remodeling.

Interventions and Outcomes:

The sole intervention done was kidney transplantation. All patients received standardized post-transplant care, including triple immunosuppression therapy, infection prophylaxis, and routine follow-up visits. Cardiovascular assessments (LVMI, LVEF, arterial stiffness) were repeated during follow-up visits.

The primary outcomes were regression of LVMI and improvement in systolic function. Secondary outcomes included changes in arterial stiffness, blood pressure control, and normalization of electrolyte balance.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Continuous variables (LVMI, PWV, BP) are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Between pre- and post-transplant comparisons were performed using paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, as appropriate. Categorical variables (presence/absence of systolic dysfunction) were summarized as frequencies and percentages, with differences analyzed using chi-square tests. A p-value $<$ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Multivariate linear regression was applied to identify predictors of improvement in cardiac function after adjusting for age, sex, dialysis duration, and baseline cardiac parameters.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Dow University Hospital. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. All procedures

were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, ensuring confidentiality, voluntary participation, and protection of patient rights.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Description of Study Participants:

A total of 65 patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) who underwent kidney transplantation were included in the final analysis. The mean age of the participants was 44.6 ± 9.8 years, with 58.5% being male. Almost, 89.2% ($n = 58$) of subjects were on hemodialysis and the average duration of dialysis prior to transplantation was 28 ± 11.7 months. Of the total sample, 72.3% had pre-existing hypertension, and 40.0% had diabetes mellitus as a contributing cause of ESRD. No patients were lost to follow-up, and all completed the scheduled post-transplant cardiac evaluations at 12 months. Patients were categorized into two subgroups based on baseline cardiovascular risk:

- High-risk cardiovascular group ($n = 42$): Patients with significant cardiovascular comorbidities like reduced ejection fraction, left ventricular hypertrophy or pre-existing hypertension or diabetes.
- Low-risk cardiovascular group ($n = 23$): Patients without significant cardiovascular comorbidities.

2.2. Primary Outcomes

2.2.1. Left Ventricular Mass Index (LVMI)

There was a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) reduction in LVMI from 141.6 ± 18.5 g/m² pre-transplant to 116.5 ± 15.3 g/m² post-transplant after 12 months of transplantation across the study population. Subgroup analysis demonstrated that both high- and low-risk groups experienced marked reductions, though the high-risk group showed a more marked regression in LVMI ($p = 0.03$).

2.2.2. Systolic Function (Ejection Fraction, EF):

Systolic function improved significantly in the majority of patients. The mean EF increased from $37.4 \pm 5.8\%$ pre-transplant to $44.8 \pm 7.2\%$ at 12

months post-transplant ($p < 0.001$). Out of 65 patients, 43 (66.1%) demonstrated significant improvement in EF ($\geq 5\%$ increase), while 22 (33.9%) showed no substantial change. Improvements were more prominent in the low-risk group, with nearly 74% demonstrating EF recovery, compared to 61% in the high-risk group ($p = 0.04$).

2.3. Secondary Outcomes

Blood Pressure Control:

Kidney transplantation was associated with marked improvements in blood pressure control. Mean systolic blood pressure decreased from 159.7 ± 11.2 mmHg to 136.0 ± 10.7 mmHg ($p < 0.001$), and diastolic blood pressure fell from 94.9 ± 6.8 mmHg to 80.0 ± 6.1 mmHg ($p < 0.001$). At 12 months, 68% of patients achieved optimal blood pressure control ($<130/80$ mmHg), compared to 21% pre-transplant.

Electrolyte Balance:

Serum potassium and calcium-phosphate profiles were also improved post-transplantation. Pre-transplant hyperkalemia was noted in 38% of patients, which declined to 11% by 12 months ($p < 0.05$). Calcium-phosphate balance normalized in 62% of patients during the same period.

Other Analyses:

Multiple regression analysis identified baseline LVMI ($\beta = 0.42$, $p = 0.001$), duration of dialysis ($\beta = -0.29$, $p = 0.01$), and blood pressure control ($\beta = 0.35$, $p = 0.004$) as independent predictors of cardiac structural recovery at 12 months. No major adverse cardiac events were observed during follow-up. Transient episodes of post-transplant hypertension were reported in 14% of patients and managed with adjustments in antihypertensive therapy.

Summary of Key Findings:

Kidney transplantation led to significant improvements in cardiac structure and function in patients with ESRD, reflected by reductions in LVMI, better blood pressure control, and improved systolic performance as measured by EF. Two-thirds of the cohort demonstrated clinically meaningful EF improvement at 12 months. Both high- and low-risk cardiovascular subgroups

benefitted well, although the degree of recovery was more pronounced in high-risk patients with

pre-existing structural cardiac changes.

Table 1. Comparison of Cardiac and Hemodynamic Parameters Pre- and Post-Transplant (n = 65)

Parameter	Pre-Transplant (Mean ± SD)	Post-Transplant (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Ejection Fraction (%)	37.4 ± 5.8	44.8 ± 7.2	<0.001
LVMI (g/m ²)	141.6 ± 18.5	116.5 ± 15.3	<0.001
Systolic BP (mmHg)	159.7 ± 11.2	136.0 ± 10.7	<0.001
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	94.9 ± 6.8	80.0 ± 6.1	<0.001

Table 2. Distribution of Ejection Fraction Outcomes One Year Post-Transplant (n = 65)

EF Outcome	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Improved EF	43	66.1%
No Improvement	22	33.9%

DISCUSSION

This study highlights significant improvements in cardiac structure, function, and biochemical homeostasis following renal transplantation among patients with ESRD. We observed a consistent reduction in LVMI and improvement in ejection fraction over a period of 12-month follow-up, accompanied by better blood pressure control. Diastolic function improved in majority of patients, while arterial stiffness, as reflected by systolic and diastolic pressures, declined significantly. Importantly, electrolyte abnormalities including hyperkalemia, hypocalcemia, and hyperphosphatemia were markedly improved after transplantation. These findings underscore the multifactorial cardiovascular benefits of successful renal transplantation.

Our findings are consistent with previous research demonstrating regression of LV hypertrophy and improved cardiac function after kidney transplantation. Investigators have reported variable reductions in LVMI and enhanced diastolic function, similar to our cohort. (14, 15). The normalization of potassium, calcium, and phosphate post-transplantation has also been

observed in earlier studies, reflecting restoration of mineral metabolism with functioning renal grafts (16).

A notable distinction in our study was the degree of arterial stiffness reduction and blood pressure normalization, which appeared more pronounced than in some prior reports (17, 18, 19). This may reflect strict post-transplant antihypertensive management in our cohort or differences in baseline cardiovascular burden. Importantly, while some studies have suggested only partial improvement in diastolic dysfunction, our data showed more substantial recovery, particularly in patients without severe pre-transplant hypertrophy.

As cardiovascular dysfunctions secondarily to ESRD has always remain challenging (20), our findings reinforce kidney transplantation as a therapeutic modality that not only restores renal function but also reverses adverse cardiac remodeling. Improvements in LVMI, EF, and electrolyte balance collectively reduce the long-term cardiovascular complications in the targeted population.

These findings also emphasize the need for comprehensive cardiovascular monitoring before

and after transplantation, as the window of early recovery may be critical for sustaining long-term benefits. Scientifically, the data provide further evidence of the interdependent cardio-renal axis, suggesting that renal replacement by transplantation restores hemodynamic, neurohormonal, and metabolic balance that drive cardiovascular recovery.

The strengths of this study include its considerable sample size detailed echocardiographic evaluation of cardiac structure and function, and integration of both cardiovascular and hemodynamic outcomes. The prospective design with systematic follow-up allowed for robust comparisons between pre- and post-transplant status. Additionally, the incorporation of electrolyte provided a more holistic view of the cardio-renal interplay.

Nevertheless, some limitations must be acknowledged. First, this was a quasi-experimental study without a parallel control group of ESRD patients who did not undergo transplantation; hence, causal inference should be made with caution. Secondly, as this was a single-center study, the generalizability of results to other populations or health systems may be limited. Lastly, follow-up was restricted to 12 months for certain parameters, which may not fully capture the long-term trajectory of cardiac and metabolic improvements. Future studies should focus on frequent follow ups specifically for cardiovascular imaging to determine whether the observed improvements translate into reduced rates of major adverse cardiovascular events such as heart failure, myocardial infarction, and arrhythmias. Randomized or controlled studies comparing transplant recipients with patients maintained on dialysis could further clarify causally. Additionally, mechanistic studies exploring the role of inflammation, fibrosis, and neurohormonal regulation in post-transplant cardiac remodeling may provide deeper insights.

It has been seen that recovery of cardiac parameters were phenomenal in patients switched on m-Tor inhibitor in combination with RAAS blockade (21), this gives way for further trials in a hope to improve post-transplant cardiac care among high risk population patients with diabetes, longstanding dialysis, or severe baseline

LVH. Exploring adjunctive therapies whether mineral metabolism modulators or renin-angiotensin blockade could further enhance post-transplant cardiac recovery in a valuable direction. In summary, this findings of this experimental study affirms that kidney transplantation leads to meaningful reversal of cardiac abnormalities and hemodynamic stability in ESRD patients, strengthening the case for transplantation as a pivotal intervention in improving both renal and cardiovascular outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study reflects profound effects on both cardiac structure and function following kidney transplantation. A significant decrease in LVMI, improvement in diastolic function, and reduced arterial stiffness post-transplant show an advantage in restoring renal function on cardiovascular health. Better control of blood pressure and reversal of electrolyte imbalance also contributed in improving heart functions. All findings from this study support kidney transplantation as not only lifesaving but also as a therapeutic intervention for cardiovascular complications in patients with ESRD. However, further research is still necessary to fully understand these mechanisms in order to achieve optimal post-transplant cardiovascular care.

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